

Endoscopic Septoplasty Methods in Modern Interpretation

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Abstract: The role of the nasal septum in the functioning of the nose and its paranasal sinuses is invaluable. Many people cannot boast of a perfectly straight nasal septum, although it is often slightly bent and the defect is not considered a pathology. There are people with a pronounced curvature of the nasal septum.

Keywords: Endoscopic microsurgery as an effective method of nasal septum repair, Traditional approach of surgeons for nasal septum repair.

There are many causes of curvature, all of them are divided into 2 categories: mechanical and physiological.

The first includes various injuries, and the second includes individual characteristics of the body. If everything is more or less clear with mechanical damage, physiological damage requires accuracy. Thus, the reason for this curvature is the different growth rate of the outer part of the nose and the nasal septum. Sometimes the septum is replaced by other intranasal structures that have increased in size.

If a deviated septum interferes with normal breathing and sinus ventilation, surgery may be necessary.

In addition, most of the septum can be smooth, but one of its sections has a spike or ridge located on the side wall of the nose. Such contact is undesirable, although at first it does not interfere with nasal breathing, it leads to a long duration of cold, and also causes complications such as otitis or sinusitis. In such cases, some time after the onset of chronic rhinitis, characteristic disturbances in nasal breathing can be observed, which in turn is caused by constant pressure from the deviation of the nasal septum.

In such cases, patients are often cautious and surprised when they receive an offer from the doctor to correct the nasal septum. And all because they do not fully understand that this is the problem that caused the development of the disease.

The traditional approach of surgeons to repair the nasal septum

As a rule, surgeons use a traditional approach to repair the nasal septum, which includes:

Repair of the septum is only in the breathing zone, that is, in the lower part. The disadvantage of this operation is that the violation of the ventilation of the paranasal sinuses is ignored, because the upper part of the septum is preserved.

Complete removal of curved areas, as a result of which it is impossible to preserve the base of the septum.

If, in addition to deviation of the septum, the patient also has sinusitis, the operation is divided into several stages, that is, it is not performed in one day.

From the above, we can conclude that in most cases, the traditional approach to solving the problem of deviation of the nasal septum is not the most optimal solution. Especially when more progressive treatments are available.

Endoscopic microsurgery as an effective method of nasal septum correction

An experienced doctor working with endoscopic surgery can correct the nasal septum, which avoids any defects.

Our treatment strategy is based on the following principles:

Deviation of the nasal septum is not a reason for surgery. We know when to fix and when not to.

We welcome gentle endoscopic techniques that involve the repair of a certain part of the septum, in which a large part of it is preserved.

We guarantee the complete restoration of normal breathing of the nose, because at the same time as the septum correction, we carry out a slight correction of other anatomical structures. We are sure that only this approach guarantees long-term and reliable results.

Treatment

Treatment of runny nose (chronic rhinitis: allergic, vasomotor or medicinal)

Treatment of deviated nasal septum (septoplasty)

Treatment of nasal polyposis and polyposis sinusitis

Treatment of chronic sinusitis, ethmoiditis, frontal sinusitis, sphenoiditis

Treatment of sinus cysts and polyps

Treatment of chronic tonsillitis

Treatment of adenoids and chronic adenoiditis

Treatment of regular snoring and snoring with sleep apnea syndrome

Treatment of lacrimal duct obstruction and chronic dacryocystitis

Treatment of acute otitis and exacerbation of chronic otitis

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